

Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of 3-[4'-Alkoxyphenyl] and 3-[4'-Arylalkoxyphenyl]sydnones and their Derivatives

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Several 3-[4'-alkoxyphenyl] and 3-[4'-arylalkoxyphenyl]sydnones and their 4-acetyl and 4-bromo derivatives have been synthesised. The compounds have been characterised by elemental and spectral analysis and screened for antimicrobial activity.

3-Arylsydnones have been known to possess a wide spectrum of biological properties^{1,2}. Moreover, such compounds were found less toxic than the 3-alkylsydnones². Tien *et al.*³ synthesised 3-[3'-methoxybenzyl]sydnone and its 4-[morpholinomethyl] analogue which showed coronary dilating, local anaesthetic, cardiotropic, anticonvulsant, muscle relaxant and behaviour depressant activity. In a view of this fact, it was thought of interest to synthesise 3-[4'-alkoxyphenyl] and 3-[4'-arylalkoxyphenyl]sydnones (4), their 4-acetyl (5) and 4-bromo (6) derivatives (Scheme 1) and to study their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman Acculab spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (CDCl₃) at 90 MHz on a EM-360 Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc in benzene and ethyl acetate as eluent (9 : 1) and the spots were visualised by iodine vapour.

3-[4'-*n*-Alkoxy/4'-arylalkoxyphenyl]sydnones⁴ (4a—e): The *N*-nitrosoglycine (3; 5.0 g) dissolved in acetic anhydride (25 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 6 h. The mixture was then cooled and poured onto crushed ice with stirring. The resulting mixture was neutralised with liquor ammonia, and the separated solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (60–80°): 4a (68%), m.p. 93–95° (Found: N, 12.31. C₁₁H₁₂N₂O₃ requires: N, 12.72%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1760 (C=O) and 3130 cm⁻¹ (sydnone C—H); m/z 221 ($M+H^+$) (26.26%), 220 (2.15), 190 (41.93), 162 (100), 135 (15), 120 (45.16) and 93 (31.18); δ 6.9 (1H, s, sydnone CH) and 7.1–7.7 (4H, sym d, PhH); 4b (63%), m.p. 84–85°; 4c (67%), 154–55°; 4d (69%), 146–48°; 4e (64%), 129–30°.

4-Acetyl-3-(4'-*n*-alkoxyphenyl) sydnones⁵ (5a, b): To a suspension of phosphorous pentoxide (21.3 g, 0.15 mol) and sodium-dried benzene (125 ml), was added 4 (0.05 mol). The stirred mixture was

Scheme 1

refluxed and glacial acetic acid (2.86 ml, 0.05 mol) was added dropwise within a period of 10 min and then refluxed for 5 h during which the resultant solution turned brown-black. After cooling to room temperature, benzene was decanted and the remaining black residue was washed with benzene (2×20 ml). The combined washings and decantate was evaporated to dryness to yield a solid which was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°): **5a** (47%), m.p. 67° (Found: N, 10.56. $C_{13}H_{14}N_2O_3$ requires: N, 10.68%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1760–1725 (sydnone C=O) and 1670–1665 cm^{-1} (acyl C=O); δ 2.5 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.0–7.5 (4H, sym d, PhH) and 4.0 (2H, t, OCH₂); **5b** (40%), m.p. 75°.

4-Bromo-3-(4'-n-alkoxy/4'-arylakoxyphenyl) sydnones⁶ (6a, 6c–e): To the sydnones (4; 0.01 mol) in ethanol (12 ml) was added sodium bicarbonate (0.924 g, 0.011 mol) in water (9 ml). To it a solution of bromine (11.98 g, 0.011 mol) in ethanol (9 ml) was added dropwise with stirring over 5 min. After a further 30 min, the mixture was poured into water (40 ml) and the resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol: **6a** (75%), m.p. 78–80° (Found: N, 9.05. $C_{11}H_{11}BrN_2O_3$ requires: N, 9.37%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1760 cm^{-1} (sydnone C=O); **6c** (68%), m.p. 158–60°; **6d** (68%), 118°; **6e** (65%), 88–89°.

All compounds (4–6) gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial activity⁷ of the compounds (4) was determined against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus*

vulgaris, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at a dose level of 180 $\mu g/0.18$ ml, following the agar plate diffusion method⁸. Dimethyl formamide was used as a solvent to prepare the solutions.

All the compounds (4) showed a broad spectrum of antimicrobial activity against all the organisms, but were less effective than the standard (sulfonamide, phenol and benzylpenicillin). Compound **3a** was found to be the most active against *E. coli*, and **4c** the most active against *P. aeruginosa*.

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